

UNICORE GATEWAY

UNICORE Team

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This user manual provides information on running and using the UNICORE 6 gateway. Please note also the following places for getting more information:

UNICORE Website: <http://www.unicore.eu>

Support list: unicore-support@lists.sf.net

Developer's list: unicore-devel@lists.sf.net

1 Introduction

The Gateway is the entry point into a UNICORE site. It is installed in front of any networking firewall. It authenticates incoming messages and forwards them to their intended destination. The gateway receives the reply and sends it back to the client.

In effect, traffic to a *virtual* URL, e.g. `https://mygateway:8088/Alpha` is forwarded to the real URL, e.g. `https://host1:7777`. In this way, only a single open port in a site's firewall has to be configured. (Technical note: this process only works for "most" HTTP requests (i.e. POST, GET and PUT), and is not a complete HTTP reverse proxy implementation).

The mappings of virtual URL to real URL for the available sites are listed in a configuration file `connections.properties`. Additionally, the gateway supports dynamic registration of sites.

The second functionality of the gateway is authentication of incoming requests. Connections to the gateway are made using client-authenticated SSL, so the gateway will check whether the caller presents a certificate issued by a trusted authority. Information about the authenticated client is forwarded to services behind the gateway in UNICORE proprietary format (as SOAP header element).

IMPORTANT NOTE ON PATHS

The UNICORE Gateway is distributed either as a platform independent and portable bundle (as a part of the UNICORE core server package) or as an installable, platform dependent package format such as RPM.

Depending on the installation method, the paths to various Gateway files are different. If installing using a distribution-specific package the following paths are used:

```
CONF=/etc/unicore/gateway
BIN=/usr/sbin
LOG=/var/log/unicore/gateway
```

If installing using the portable bundle all Gateway files are installed under a single directory. Path prefixes then are as follows, where INST is a directory where the Gateway was installed:

```
CONF=INST/conf
BIN=INST/bin
LOG=INST/log
```

The above variables (CONF, BIN and LOG) are used throughout the rest of this manual.

2 Installation

The UNICORE Gateway is distributed in the following formats:

1. As a part of platform independent installation bundle called UNICORE core server bundle. The UNICORE core server bundle is provided in two forms: one with a graphical installer and one with a command line installer.
2. As a binary, platform-specific packages available currently for the Debian, Scientific Linux 5, and Scientific Linux 6 platforms. Those packages are tested on the enumerated platforms, but should work without any problems with other versions of similar distributions (e.g. version for SL6 works well on Centos 6 or recent Fedora distributions. Differences between SL5 and SL6 version are only in the RPM tools used to create packages (so SL5 version should be more universal, while SL6 version may require a newer rpm software).

2.1 Installation from the core server bundle

Download the core server bundle from the UNICORE project website.

If you use the graphical installer, follow the on-screen instructions and do not forget to enable the Gateway checkbox when prompted.

If you use the console installer, please review the README file available after extracting the bundle. You don't have to change any defaults as the Gateway is installed by default.

2.2 Installation from RPM package (RedHat distributions)

The preferred way is to use Yum to install (and subsequently update) the Gateway.

To perform the Yum installation, EMI Yum repository must be installed first. Refer to the EMI release documentation (available at the EMI website <http://www.eu-emi.eu/releases>) for detailed instructions. Typically installation of the EMI repository requires to download a single RPM file and install it.

After the EMI repository is configured, the following command installs Gateway:

```
$> yum install unicore-gateway
```

2.3 Installation from the DEB package (Debian distributions)

The preferred installation way is to use apt to install and subsequently update the Gateway.

To perform the apt installation, EMI apt repository must be installed first. Refer to the EMI release documentation (available at the EMI website <http://www.eu-emi.eu/releases>) for detailed

instructions. Typically installation of the EMI repository requires to download a single DEB file and install it.

After the EMI repository is configured, the following command installs the Gateway:

```
$> apt-get install unicore-gateway
```

3 Upgrade from to 6.5.0 version

Gateway 6.5.0 (released in UNICORE quickstart 6.6.0) introduces a lot of new features and therefore the update from the previous version requires special attention as configuration files format have changed for `gateway.properties` and `security.properties`. What's more `crlcheck.properties` file is obsolete and not used any more: CRL settings are provided in `security.properties`.

The general update procedure is presented below, with possible variations:

1. Stop the old Gateway.
2. Update the server package. This step mostly applies for RPM/DEB managed installations. For Quickstart installation it is advised to install Gateway along with other needed components to a separate directory.
3. Port configuration of pre-1.5.0 server to the new syntax. It can be done in two ways:
 - Manually by applying all old values to the new template configuration. There are quite a few properties to be ported so this requires several minutes of work. The advantage of manual porting is that the new template files with new options and updated comments are used. Note: for RPM installations the new files will be named `*.rpmnew`.
 - Automatically, using UNICORE configurator. You have to install the `unicore-configurator` package. It is included in Quickstart, for distributions install simply run appropriate command: `yum install unicore-configurator` or `apt-get install unicore-configurator`. Using the configurator you can update the old files automatically:
 - For RPM/DEB installations it is enough to run `unicore-config-update.py gateway`.
 - For Quickstart put your old configuration files in the folder with the newly installed Gateway and specify its directory with `-c` option: `./unicore-config-update.py -c GATEWAY_CONFIG_DIR gateway`. Carefully read the output of the program - there can be some problems reported. Option `-h` provides help, with information about the usage: how to perform dry run, how to recover files from backup etc.
4. Start the newly installed Gateway.
5. Verify log file and fix any problems reported.

4 Configuration

The gateway is configured using a set of configuration files, which reside in the `CONF` subdirectory.

4.1 Java and environment settings: `startup.properties`

This file contains settings related to the Java VM, such as the Java command to use, memory settings, library paths etc.

4.2 Configuring sites: `connections.properties`

This is a simple list connecting the names of sites and their physical addresses. An example is:

```
DEMO-SITE = https://localhost:7777
REGISTRY = https://localhost:7778
```

If this file is modified, the gateway will re-read it at runtime, so there is no need to restart the gateway in order to add or remove sites.

Optionally administrator can enable a possibility for dynamic site registration at runtime, see Section 4.3.2 for details. Then this file should contain only the static entries (or none if all sites register dynamically).

Further options for back-end sites configuration are presented in Section 6.

4.3 Main server settings: `gateway.properties`

Use the `gateway.hostname` property to configure the network interface and port the gateway will listen on. You can also select between `https` and `http` protocol, though in almost all cases `https` will be used.

Example:

```
gateway.hostname = https://192.168.100.123:8080
```

Note

If you set the host to `0.0.0.0`, the gateway will listen on all network interfaces of the host machine, else it will listen only on the specified one.

If the scheme of the hostname URL is set to `https`, the Gateway uses the configuration data from `security.properties` to configure the HTTPS settings.

4.3.1 Scalability settings

To fine-tune the operational parameters of the embedded Jetty server, you can set advanced HTTP server parameters. See Section 4.3.5 for details. Among others you can use the non-blocking IO connector offered by Jetty, which will scale up to higher numbers of concurrent connections than the default connector.

The gateway acts as a https client for the VSites behind it. The number of concurrent calls is limited, and controlled by two parameters:

```
# maximum total number of concurrent calls to Vsites
gateway.client.maxTotal=100
# total number of concurrent calls per site
gateway.client.maxPerService=20
```

You can also control the limit on the maximum SOAP header size which is allowed by the gateway. **Typically you don't have to touch this parameter.** However if your clients do produce very big SOAP headers and gateway blocks them, you can increase the limit. Note that such a giant SOAP header usually means that the client is not behaving in a sane way, e.g. is trying to perform a DoS attack.

```
# maximum size of an accepted SOAP header, in bytes
gateway.soapMaxHeader=102400
```

Note that gateway may consume this amount of memory (plus some extra amount for other data) for each opened connection. Therefore, this value multiplied by the number of maximum allowed connections, should be significantly lower, than the total memory available for the gateway.

4.3.2 Dynamic registration of VSites

Dynamic registration is controlled by three properties in `CONF/gateway.properties` file:

```
gateway.registration.enable=true
```

If set to true, the gateway will accept dynamic registrations which are made by sending a HTTP POST request to the URL `/VSITE_REGISTRATION_REQUEST`

Filters can be set to forbid access of certain hosts, or to require certain strings in the Vsite addresses. For example:

```
gateway.registration.deny=foo.org example.org
```

will deny registration if the remote hostname contains *foo.org* or *example.org*. Conversely,

```
gateway.registration.allow=mydomain.org
```

will only accept registrations if the remote address contains *mydomain.org*. These two (deny and allow) can be combined.

4.3.3 Web interface ("monkey page")

For testing and simple monitoring purposes, the gateway displays a website showing detailed site information (the details view can be disabled). Once the Gateway is running, open up a browser and navigate to https://<gateway_host>:8080 (or whichever URL the gateway is running on). As the gateway usually runs using SSL, you will need to import a suitable client certificate into your web browser.

A HTML form for testing the dynamic registration is available as well, by clicking the link in the footer of the main gateway page.

To disable the Vsite details page, set

```
gateway.disableWebpage=true
```

4.3.4 Main options reference

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
gateway.hostname	string	<i>mandatory to be set</i>	external gateway bind address
gateway.registration.allow	string	-	Space separated list of allowed hosts for dynamic registration.
gateway.registration.deny	string	-	Space separated list of denied hosts for dynamic registration.
gateway.registration.enable	[true, false]	false	Whether dynamic registration of sites is enabled.
<i>--- Passing Consignor info ---</i>			
gateway.consignorTokenTimeTolerance	integer >= 0	30	The validity time of the authenticated client information passed to backend sites will start that many seconds before the real authentication. It is used to mask time synchronization problems between machines.

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
gateway.consignorTokenValidity	integer >= 1	60	What is the validity time of the authenticated client information passed to backend sites. Increase it if there machines clocks are not synhronized.
gateway.signConsignorToken	[true, false]	false	Controls whether information about the authenticated client (the consignor) passed to backend sites should be signed, or not. Signing is slower, but is required when sites may be reached directly, bypassing the Gateway.
<i>--- Gateway → Site client ---</i>			
gateway.client.chunked	[true, false]	true	Controls whether chunked passing of HTTP requests to backend sites is supported.
gateway.client.connectionTimeout	integer number	30000	Connection timeout, used when connecting to backend sites.
gateway.client.expectContinue	[true, false]	true	Controls whether the HTTP expec-continue mechanism is enaled on connections to backend sites.
gateway.client.gzip	[true, false]	true	Controls whether support for compression is announced to backend sites.
gateway.client.keepAlive	[true, false]	true	Whether to keep alive the connections to backend sites.
gateway.client.maxPerService	integer number	20	Maximum allowed number of connections per backend site.
gateway.client.maxTotal	integer number	100	Maximum total number of connections to backend sites allowed.
gateway.client.socketTimeout	integer number	30000	Connection timeout, used when connecting to backend sites.

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
<i>--- Advanced ---</i>			
gateway.disableWebpage	[true, false]	false	Whether the (so called monkey) status web page should be disabled.
gateway.externalHostname	string	<i>not set</i>	External address of the gateway, when it is accessible through a frontend server as Apache HTTP.
gateway.protocolPlugin.*	list of properties with a common prefix	<i>not set</i>	Subkey of this property should be a protocol name in capital letters and value should contain the class of a plugin implementing it.
gateway.soapMaxHeader	integer [1024 — 1024000000]	102400	Size in bytes of the accepted SOAP header. In the most cases you don't need to change it.

4.3.5 Configuring advanced HTTP server settings

UNICORE servers are using an embedded Jetty HTTP server. In most cases the default configuration should be perfectly fine. However, for some sites (e.g. experiencing an extremely high load) HTTP server settings can be fine-tuned with the following parameters.

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
gateway.httpServer.ajp	[true, false]	false	Controls whether AJP support (using Apache server as frontend) is enabled.
gateway.httpServer.disabledCipherSuites	string	<i>empty string</i>	Space separated list of SSL cipher suites to be disabled.
gateway.httpServer.fastRandom	[true, false]	false	Use insecure, but fast pseudo random generator to generate session ids instead of secure generator for SSL sockets.
gateway.httpServer.gzip.enable	[true, false]	false	Controls whether to enable compression of HTTP responses.

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
gateway. httpServer.gzip. minGzipSize	integer number	100000	Specifies the minimal size of message that should be compressed.
gateway. httpServer.highLoadConnections	integer >= 1	200	If the number of connections exceeds this amount, then the connector is put into a special <i>low on resources</i> state. Existing connections will be closed faster. Note that this value is honored only for NIO connectors. Legacy connectors go into low resources mode when no more threads are available.
gateway. httpServer. lowResourceMaxIdleTime	integer >= 1	100	In low resource conditions, time (in ms.) before an idle connection will time out.
gateway. httpServer. maxIdleTime	integer >= 1	200000	Time (in ms.) before an idle connection will time out. It should be large enough not to expire connections with slow clients, values below 30s are getting quite risky.
gateway. httpServer. maxThreads	integer >= 1	255	Maximum number of threads to have in the thread pool for processing HTTP connections.
gateway. httpServer. minThreads	integer >= 1	1	Minimum number of threads to have in the thread pool for processing HTTP connections.
gateway. httpServer.requireClientAuthn	[true, false]	true	Controls whether the SSL socket requires client-side authentication.
gateway. httpServer. soLingerTime	integer number	-1	Socket linger time.

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
gateway. httpServer. useNIO	[true, false]	false	Controls whether the NIO connector be used. NIO is best suited under high-load, when lots of connections exist that are idle for long periods.
gateway. httpServer. wantClientAuthn	[true, false]	true	Controls whether the SSL socket accepts (but does not require) client-side authentication.

Example

Note

Various UNICORE modules use different property prefixes. Here we don't put any, but in practice you have to use the prefix (see the reference table above for the actual prefix). Also properties might need to be provided using different syntax, as XML.

In this example we will turn on compression of all responses bigger then 50kB (assuming that the client supports decompression). Additionally we are limiting the number of concurrent clients that can be served to more or less 50, while keeping 10 threads ready all the time to server new clients quicker.

```
jetty.gzip.enable=true
jetty.gzip.minGzipSize=51200
jetty.maxThreads=50
jetty.minThreads=10
```

4.4 security.properties

In the `security.properties` file, the trust store and gateway credential is configured.

4.4.1 Configuring PKI trust settings

Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) trust settings are used to validate certificates. This is performed, in the first place when a connection with a remote peer is initiated over the network, using the SSL (or TLS) protocol. Additionally certificate validation can happen in few other situations, e.g. when checking digital signatures of various sensitive pieces of data.

Certificates validation is primarily configured using a set of initially trusted certificates of so called Certificate Authorities (CAs). Those trusted certificates are also known as *trust anchors* and their collection is called a *trust store*.

Except of *trust anchors* validation mechanism can use additional input for checking if a certificate being checked was not revoked and if its subject is in a permitted namespace.

UNICORE allows for different types of trust stores. All of them are configured using a set of properties.

- *Keystore trust store* - the only format supported in older UNICORE versions. Trusted certificates are stored in a single binary file in JKS or PKCS12 format. The file can be only manipulated using a special tool like JDK *keytool* or openssl (in case of PKCS12 format). This format is great if trust store should be in a single file or when compatibility with other Java solutions or older UNICORE releases is desired.
- *OpenSSL trust store* - allows to use a directory with CA certificates stored in PEM format, under precisely defined names: the CA certificates, CRLs, signing policy files and namespaces files are named <hash>.0, <hash>.r0, <hash>.signing_policy and <hash>.namespaces. Hash is the old hash of the trusted CA certificate subject name (in Openssl version > 1.0.0 use -subject_hash_old switch to generate it). If multiple certificates have the same hash then the default zero number must be increased. This format is the same as used by other then UNICORE popular middlewares as Globus and gLite. It is suggested when a common trust store with such middlewares is needed.
- *Directory trust store* - the most flexible and convenient option, suggested for all remaining cases. It allows to use a list of wildcard expressions, concrete paths of files or even URLs to remote files as a set of trusted CAs and in the same way for the CRLs. With this trust store administrator can simply configure all files (or all with a specified extension) in a directory to be used as a trusted certificates.

In all cases trust stores can be (and by default are) configured to be automatically refreshed.

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
gateway.truststore.allowProxy	[ALLOW, DENY]	ALLOW	Controls whether proxy certificates are supported.
gateway.truststore.type	[keystore, openssl, directory]	<i>mandatory to be set</i>	The truststore type.
gateway.truststore.updateInterval	integer number	600	How often the truststore should be reloaded, in seconds. Set to negative value to disable refreshing at runtime. (<i>runtime updateable</i>)

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
<i>--- Directory type settings ---</i>			
gateway. truststore. directoryConnectionTimeout	integer number	15	Connection timeout for fetching the remote CA certificates in seconds.
gateway. truststore. directoryDiskCachePath	filesystem path	-	Directory where CA certificates should be cached, after downloading them from a remote source. Can be left undefined if no disk cache should be used. Note that directory should be secured, i.e. normal users should not be allowed to write to it.
gateway. truststore.directoryEncoding	[PEM, DER]	PEM	For directory truststore controls whether certificates are encoded in PEM or DER.
gateway. truststore.directoryLocations.*	list of properties with a common prefix	-	List of CA certificates locations. Can contain URLs, local files and wildcard expressions. <i>(runtime updateable)</i>
<i>--- Keystore type settings ---</i>			
gateway. truststore. keystoreFormat	string	-	The keystore type (jks, pkcs12) in case of truststore of keystore type.
gateway. truststore. keystorePassword	string	-	The password of the keystore type truststore.
gateway. truststore. keystorePath	string	-	The keystore path in case of truststore of keystore type.
<i>--- Openssl type settings ---</i>			

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
gateway. truststore. opensslNsMode	[GLOBUS_EUGRIDPMA, EU- GRIDPMA_GLOBUS, GLOBUS, EUGRIDPMA, GLOBUS_EUGRIDPMA_REQUIRE, EU- GRIDPMA_GLOBUS_REQUIRE, GLOBUS_REQUIRE, EU- GRIDPMA_REQUIRE, EU- GRIDPMA_AND_GLOBUS, EU- GRIDPMA_AND_GLOBUS_REQUIRE, IGNORE]	GRIDPMA, A_GLOBUS	In case of openssl truststore, controls which (and in which order) namespace checking rules should be applied. The REQUIRE settings will cause that all configured namespace definitions files must be present for each trusted CA certificate (otherwise checking will fail). The AND settings will cause to check both existing namespace files. Otherwise IGNORE , found is checked (in the order defined by the property).
gateway. truststore. opensslPath	filesystem path	/etc/ grid-sec urity/ certific ates	Directory to be used for openssl truststore.
<i>--- Revocation settings ---</i>			
gateway. truststore.crlCo nnectionTimeout	integer number	15	Connection timeout for fetching the remote CRLs in seconds (not used for Openssl truststores).
gateway. truststore. crlDiskCachePath	filesystem path	-	Directory where CRLs should be cached, after downloading them from remote source. Can be left undefined if no disk cache should be used. Note that directory should be secured, i.e. normal users should not be allowed to write to it. Not used for Openssl truststores.

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
gateway.truststore.crlLocations.*	list of properties with a common prefix	-	List of CRLs locations. Can contain URLs, local files and wildcard expressions. Not used for Openssl truststores. (<i>runtime updateable</i>)
gateway.truststore.crlMode	[REQUIRE, IF_VALID, IGNORE]	IF_VALID	General CRL handling mode. The IF_VALID setting turns on CRL checking only in case the CRL is present.
gateway.truststore.crlUpdateInterval	integer number	600	How often CRLs should be updated, in seconds. Set to negative value to disable refreshing at runtime. (<i>runtime updateable</i>)
gateway.truststore.ocspCacheTtl	integer number	3600	For how long the OCSP responses should be locally cached in seconds (this is a maximum value, responses won't be cached after expiration)
gateway.truststore.ocspDiskCache	filesystem path	-	If this property is defined then OCSP responses will be cached on disk in the defined folder.
gateway.truststore.ocspLocalResponders.<NUMBER>	list of properties with a common prefix	-	Optional list of local OCSP responders
gateway.truststore.ocspMode	[REQUIRE, IF_AVAILABLE, IGNORE]	IF_AVAILABLE	General OCSP checking mode. REQUIRE should not be used unless it is guaranteed that for all certificates an OCSP responder is defined.
gateway.truststore.ocspTimeout	integer number	10000	Timeout for OCSP connections in milliseconds.
gateway.truststore.revocationOrder	[CRL_OCSP, OCSP_CRL]	OCSP_CRL	Controls overall revocation sources order

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
gateway.truststore.revocationUseAll	[true, false]	false	Controls whether all defined revocation sources should be always checked, even if the first one already confirmed that a checked certificate is not revoked.

Examples

Note

Various UNICORE modules use different property prefixes. Here we don't put any, but in practice you have to use the prefix (see the reference table above for the actual prefix). Also properties might need to be provided using different syntax, as XML.

Directory trust store, with a minimal set of options:

```
truststore.type=directory
truststore.directoryLocations.1=/trust/dir/*.pem
truststore.crlLocations=/trust/dir/*.crl
```

Directory trust store, with a complete set of options:

```
truststore.type=directory
truststore.allowProxy=DENY
truststore.updateInterval=1234
truststore.directoryLocations.1=/trust/dir/*.pem
truststore.directoryLocations.2=http://caserver/ca.pem
truststore.directoryEncoding=PEM
truststore.directoryConnectionTimeout=100
truststore.directoryDiskCachePath=/tmp
truststore.crlLocations.1=/trust/dir/*.crl
truststore.crlLocations.2=http://caserver/crl.pem
truststore.crlUpdateInterval=400
truststore.crlMode=REQUIRE
truststore.crlConnectionTimeout=200
truststore.crlDiskCachePath=/tmp
```

Openssl trust store:

```
truststore.type=openssl
truststore.opensslPath=/truststores/openssl
truststore.opensslNsMode=EUGRIDPMA_GLOBUS_REQUIRE
```

```
truststore.allowProxy=ALLOW
truststore.updateInterval=1234
truststore.crlMode=IF_VALID
```

Java keystore used as a trust store:

```
truststore.type=keystore
truststore.keystorePath=src/test/resources/certs/truststore. ←
    jks
truststore.keystoreFormat=JKS
truststore.keystorePassword=xxxxxxx
```

4.4.2 Configuring the credential

UNICORE uses private key and a corresponding certificate (called together as a *credential*) to identify users and servers. Credentials might be provided in several formats:

- Credential can be obtained from a *keystore file*, encoded in JKS or PKCS12 format.
- Credential can be loaded as a pair of PEM files (one with private key and another with certificate),
- or from a pair of DER files,
- or even from a single file, with PEM-encoded certificates and private key (in any order).

The following table list all parameters which allows for configuring the credential. Note that nearly all options are optional. If not defined, the format is tried to be guessed. However some credential formats require additional settings. For instance if using *der* format the *keyPath* is mandatory as you need two DER files: one with certificate and one with the key (and the latter can not be guessed).

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
gateway.credential.path	filesystem path	<i>mandatory to be set</i>	Credential location. In case of <i>jks</i> , <i>pkcs12</i> and <i>pem</i> store it is the only location required. In case when credential is provided in two files, it is the certificate file path.

Property name	Type	Default value / mandatory	Description
gateway. credential. format	[jks, pkcs12, der, pem]	-	Format of the credential. It is guessed when not given. Note that <i>pem</i> might be either a PEM keystore with certificates and keys (in PEM format) or a pair of PEM files (one with certificate and second with private key).
gateway. credential. password	string	-	Password required to load the credential.
gateway. credential. keyPath	string	-	Location of the private key if stored separately from the main credential (applicable for <i>pem</i> and <i>der</i> types only),
gateway. credential. keyPassword	string	-	Private key password, which might be needed only for <i>jks</i> or <i>pkcs12</i> , if key is encrypted with different password then the main credential password.
gateway. credential. keyAlias	string	-	Keystore alias of the key entry to be used. Can be ignored if the keystore contains only one key entry. Only applicable for <i>jks</i> and <i>pkcs12</i> .

Examples

Note

Various UNICORE modules use different property prefixes. Here we don't put any, but in practice you have to use the prefix (see the reference table above for the actual prefix). Also properties might need to be provided using different syntax, as XML.

Credential as a pair of DER files:

```
credential.format=der
credential.password=the\!njs
```

```
credential.path=/etc/credentials/cert-1.der
credential.keyPath=/etc/credentials/pk-1.der
```

Credential as a JKS file (credential type can be autodetected in almost every case):

```
credential.path=/etc/credentials/server1.jks
credential.password=xxxxxxx
```

4.4.3 Proxy certificate support

The UNICORE gateway optionally accepts proxy certificates as used by other Grid middleware systems. In general, we think proxies are a bad idea, but for interoperability purposes, proxies support can be enabled. If enabled, the clients using proxies are authenticated as the initial issuer of the presented proxy certificates chain. See the above reference properties table for the actual setting.

4.5 Logging

UNICORE uses the Log4j logging framework. It is configured using a config file. By default, this file is found in components configuration directory and is named `logging.properties`. The config file is specified with a Java property `log4j.configuration` (which is set in startup script).

Several libraries used by UNICORE also use the Java utils logging facility (the output is two-lines per log entry). For convenience its configuration is also controlled in the same `logging.properties` file and is directed to the same destination as the main Log4j output.

Note

You can change the logging configuration at runtime by editing the `logging.properties` file. The new configuration will take effect a few seconds after the file has been modified.

By default, log files are written to the the LOGS directory.

The following example config file configures logging so that log files are rotated daily.

```
# Set root logger level to INFO and its only appender to A1.
log4j.rootLogger=INFO, A1

# A1 is set to be a rolling file appender with default params
log4j.appender.A1=org.apache.log4j.DailyRollingFileAppender
log4j.appender.A1.File=logs/uas.log

#configure daily rollover: once per day the uas.log will be copied
#to a file named e.g. uas.log.2008-12-24
```

```
log4j.appender.A1.DatePattern='.'yyyy-MM-dd

# A1 uses the PatternLayout
log4j.appender.A1.layout=org.apache.log4j.PatternLayout
log4j.appender.A1.layout.ConversionPattern=%d [%t] %-5p %c{1} %x - ←
    %m%n
```

Note

In Log4j, the log rotation frequency is controlled by the `DatePattern`. Check <http://logging.apache.org/log4j/1.2/apidocs/org/apache/log4j/DailyRollingFileAppender.html> for the details.

For more info on controlling the logging we refer to the log4j documentation:

- [PatternLayout](#)
- [RollingFileAppender](#)
- [DailyRollingFileAppender](#)

Log4j supports a very wide range of logging options, such as date based or size based file rollover, logging different things to different files and much more. For full information on Log4j we refer to the publicly available documentation, for example the [Log4j manual](#).

4.5.1 Logger categories, names and levels

Logger names are hierarchical. In UNICORE, prefixes are used (e.g. "unicore.security") to which the Java class name is appended. For example, the XUADB connector in UNICORE/X logs to the "unicore.security.XUADBAuthoriser" logger.

Therefore the logging output produced can be controlled in a fine-grained manner. Log levels in Log4j are (in increasing level of severity):

TRACE on this level *huge* pieces of unprocessed information are dumped, # DEBUG on this level UNICORE logs (hopefully) admin-friendly, verbose information, useful for hunting problems, # INFO standard information, not much output, # WARN warnings are logged when something went wrong (so it should be investigated), but recovery was possible, # ERROR something went wrong and operation probably failed, # FATAL something went really wrong - this is used very rarely for critical situations like server failure.

For example, to debug a security problem in the UNICORE security layer, you can set:

```
log4j.logger.unicore.security=DEBUG
```

If you are just interested in details of credentials handling, but not everything related to security you can use the following:

```
log4j.logger.unicore.security=INFO
log4j.logger.unicore.security.CredentialProperties=DEBUG
```

so the XUUDBAuthoriser will log on DEBUG level, while the other security components log on INFO level.

Note

(so the full category is printed) and turn on the general DEBUG logging for a while (on uniconore). Then interesting events can be seen and subsequently the logging configuration can be fine tuned to only show them.

The most important, root log categories used by Gateway's logging are:

unicore.gateway	General gateway logging
unicore.connections	Log IPs of clients, and the DN after the SSL handshake
unicore.httpserver	HTTP processing, Jetty server
unicore.security	Certificate details and other security

The Gateway uses the so called MDC (Mapped Diagnostic Context) to provide additional information on the client which is served. In the MDC the client's IP address and client's Distinguished Name is stored. You can control whether to attach MDC to each line by the `%X{entry} log4j` pattern entry. As the entry you can use: `clientIP` or `clientName`. For example:

```
log4j.appender.A1.layout.ConversionPattern=%d [%t] [%X{clientIP} %X ←
{clientName}] %-5p %c{1} - %m%n
```

5 AJP Connector for using Apache httpd as a frontend

If you wish to use the Apache webserver (httpd) as a frontend for the gateway (e.g. for security or fault-tolerance reasons), you can enable the AJP connector instead of the usual one.

Requirements

- Apache httpd
- mod_jk for Apache httpd

Enabling AJP13 Gateway with Jetty and mod_jk

Enable "mod_ssl" module in httpd configuration files, for instance "ssl.conf":

```
LoadModule ssl_module modules/mod_ssl.so
Listen 443
```

Enable "mod_jk" module in httpd configuration files, for instance "jk.conf":

```
LoadModule jk_module modules/mod_jk.so
JkWorkersFile "conf.d/worker.properties"
```

Define a "mod_jk" worker, to dialog with Gateway's AJP connector, in "worker.properties" configuration file as referred in the above "jk.conf":

```
worker.list=jetty
worker.jetty.port={{gateway_port}}
worker.jetty.host={{gateway_ip}}
worker.jetty.type=ajp13
worker.jetty.lbfactor=1
```

Configure a httpd virtual SSL host, dedicated to act as Gateway's frontend, in the httpd configuration files, for instance "unicore.conf". This virtual host lets the "mod_jk" worker defined above in "worker.properties", manage all the requests received and forwards the full client's certificate chain:

```
# Apache VirtualHost configuration to serve as frontend
# for an "AJP connector enabled" UNICORE6 Gateway
<VirtualHost {{frontend_ip}}:{{frontend_port}}>
  # Pass every request on this VirtualHost to the jetty worker
  # defined in mod_jk's worker properties file.
  JkMount /* jetty
  # Pass SSL_CLIENT_CERT environment variable to the AJP ↔
  connector
  JkOptions +ForwardSSLCertChain

  # Log
  ErrorLog "logs/unicore_error_log"
  TransferLog "logs/unicore_access_log"
  JkLogFile "logs/unicore_mod_jk.log"

  # Enable SSL
  SSLEngine on

  # Export SSL-related environment variables, especially ↔
  SSL_CLIENT_CERT
  # which contains client's PEM-encoded certificate
  SSLOptions +StdEnvVars +ExportCertData

  # Client have to present a valid certificate
  SSLVerifyClient require

  # Server certificate
```

```
SSLCertificateFile "{{/path/to/httpd_cert.pem}}"
SSLCertificateKeyFile "{{/path/to/httpd_key.pem}}"

# Trusted CAs
SSLCACertificateFile "{{/path/to/cacert.pem}}"
</VirtualHost>
```

On the Gateway, enable Jetty AJP connector instead of its HTTP connector in Gateway configuration file `CONF/gateway.properties`:

```
#enable AJP connector
gateway.jetty.ajp=true
```

External references

- Configuring AJP13 using `mod_jk` or `mod_proxy_ajp` - Jetty <http://wiki.eclipse.org/Jetty/Tutorial/Apache>
- The Apache Tomcat Connector - Webserver HowTo http://tomcat.apache.org/connectors-doc/webserver_howto/printer/apache.html

6 Using the Gateway for failover and/or loadbalancing of UNICORE sites

The Gateway can be used as a simple failover solution and/or loadbalancer to achieve high availability and/or higher scalability of UNICORE/X sites without additional tools.

A site definition (in `CONF/connections.properties`) can be extended, so that multiple physical servers are used for a single virtual site.

An example for such a so-called multi-site declaration in the `connections.properties` file looks as follows:

```
#declare a multisite with two physical servers

MYSITE=multisite:vsites=https://localhost:7788 https://localhost ↵
:7789
```

This will tell the gateway that the virtual site "MYSITE" is indeed a multi-site with the two given physical sites.

6.1 Configuration

Configuration options for the multi-site can be passed in two ways. On the one hand they can go into the `connections.properties` file, by putting them in the multi-site definition, separated by ";" characters:

```
#declare a multisite with parameters
MYSITE=multisite:param1=value1;param2=value2;param3=value3;...
```

The following general parameters exist

vsites	List of physical sites
strategy	Class name of the site selection strategy to use (see below)
config	Name of a file containing additional parameters

Using the "config" option, all the parameters can be placed in a separate file for enhanced readability. For example you could define in `connections.properties`:

```
#declare a multisite with parameters read from a separate file
MYSITE=multisite:config=conf/mysite-cluster.properties
```

and give the details in the file "conf/mysite-cluster.properties":

```
#example multisite configuration
vsites=https://localhost:7788 https://localhost:7789

#check site health at most every 5 seconds
strategy.healthcheck.interval=5000
```

6.2 Available Strategies

A selection strategy is used to decide where a client request will be routed. By default, the strategy is "Primary with fallback", i.e. the request will go to the first site if it is available, otherwise it will go to the second site.

Primary with fallback

This strategy is suitable for a high-availability scenario, where a secondary site takes over the work in case the primary one goes down for maintenance or due to a problem. This is the default strategy, so nothing needs to be configured to enable it. If you want to explicitly enable it anyway, set

```
strategy=primaryWithFallback
```

The strategy will select from the first two defined physical sites. The first, primary one will be used if it is available, else the second one. Health check is done on each request, but not more frequently as specified by the "strategy.healthcheck.interval" parameter. By default, this parameter is set to 5000 milliseconds.

Changes to the site health will be logged at "INFO" level, so you can see when the sites go up or down.

Round robin

This strategy is suitable for a load-balancing scenario, where a random site will be chosen from the available ones. To enable it, set

```
strategy=roundRobin
```

Changes to the site health will be logged at "INFO" level, so you can see when the sites go up or down.

It is very important to be aware that this strategy requires that all backend sites used in the pool, share a common persistence. It is because Gateway does not track clients, so particular client requests may land at different sites. This is typically solved by using a non-default, shared database for sites, such as MySQL.

Note

Currently loadbalancing of target sites is an experimental feature and is not yet fully functional. It will be improved in future UNICORE versions.

Custom strategy

You can implement and use your own failover strategy, in this case, use the name of the Java class as strategy name:

```
strategy=your_class_name
```

7 Gateway failover and migration

The Section 6 covered usage of the Gateway to provide failover of backend services. However it may be needed to guarantee high-availability for the Gateway itself or to move it to other machine in case of the original one's failure.

7.1 Gateway's migration

The Gateway does not store any state information, therefore its migration is easy. It is enough to install the Gateway at the target machine (or even to simply copy it in the case of installation from the core server bundle) and to make sure that the original Gateway's configuration is preserved.

If the new machine uses a different address, it needs to be reflected in the server's configuration file (the listen address). Also, the configuration of sites behind the gateway must be updated accordingly.

7.2 Failover and loadbalancing of the Gateway

Gateway itself doesn't provide any features related to its own redundancy. However as it is stateless, the standard redundancy solutions can be used.

The simplest solution is to use Round Robin DNS, where DNS server routes the Gateway's DNS address to a pool of real IP addresses. While easy to set up this solution has a significant drawback: DNS server doesn't care about machines being down.

The much better choice is to use the Linux-HA software suite, often known under the name of its principal component, the *heartbeat*. For details see <http://www.linux-ha.org>

Additionally a more advanced HTTP-aware software can be used, such as HA-Proxy (<http://haproxy.1wt.eu>). Currently Gateway and UNICORE don't maintain HTTP sessions so usage of the HTTP-aware load-balancer is not strictly required, but such solutions generally provide more general purpose features.

8 Gateway plugins

Note

This functionality is not supported when the NIO connectors are enabled in Jetty.

The gateway supports tunneling other protocols through its socket. This is still experimental, so use at your own risk. To establish the tunnel, a special HTTP message is sent to the gateway:

```
HEAD / HTTP/1.1
Upgrade: YOURPROTOCOLNAME
```

the method must be "HEAD", and the message must contain the "Upgrade" header. The gateway replies:

```
HTTP/1.1 101 Switching protocols
Upgrade: YOURPROTOCOLNAME
```

After this the gateway's socket connection is passed to a custom handler, which can read data from the client and write replies. The handler can be configured in `CONF/gateway.properties`:

```
protocolPlugin.YOURPROTOCOLNAME=your.handler.classname
```

The handler class must implement the `eu.unicore.gateway.util.ProtocolPluginHandler` interface. For more details please refer to the sourcecode of the plugin interface class.

9 Building the Gateway from source

To checkout the latest version of the Gateway source code, do

```
svn co http://unicore.svn.sourceforge.net/svnroot/unicore/gateway/ ↵  
trunk gateway
```

You will need to install Maven from <http://maven.apache.org> Compile using

```
mvn install
```

Compiles the code and runs the tests.

```
mvn assembly:assembly
```

builds distribution archives in zip and tar.gz format in the target/ directory